

ACTN Service Orchestration of Cloud and Network Resources to support Network Slicing and Telemetry.

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Abstraction and Control of Traffic Engineered networks (ACTN) has been driving SDN standardization in IETF in the TEAS WG. This presentation gives the overview of ACTN and proposes ACTN service orchestration of cloud and network resources to support dynamic virtual network slicing including telemetry.

ACTN allows customers to request a virtual network over operator's transport networks that are often multi-layer and multi-domain TE networks. The resources granted for a virtual network in the operator's TE networks are referred to as a network slice, which is presented as an abstract topology to customers. The customers would make use of this abstracted topology to offer applications over its virtual network (e.g., on-line gaming, virtual mobile networks).

This presentation presents:

- An end-to-end automated orchestration with the joint optimization of cloud and network resources, which the applications consume in distributed data centers.
- Application-specific telemetry system that dynamically subscribes and publishes key performance data from both networks and Data Center networks.
- The usage of telemetry data in an autonomous orchestrator that allows the dynamic re-optimization and reconfiguration of the allocated resources.

